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ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS WITH CHILDREN IN THE 2ND YEAR OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL I – REPORTS OF EDUCATIONAL PRACTICES WITH THE JATAÍ STINGLESS BEE AND CONSTRUCTION OF HOLISTIC VIEWS ON NATURE

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Abstract

Formal environmental education can be promoted through experiences where children explore and interpret their surroundings, emphasizing respect and care for living beings and their interconnections. This study reports educational practices in an environmental awareness with second-grade elementary school children in a private Brazilian school. The focus was on the study of the stingless bee species *Tetragonisca angustula* (commonly known as Jataí) to foster holistic views of nature within the BEESNESS project. Learning strategies were developed through discussions with academics and institutions involved in BEESNESS, providing a scientific foundation for environmental awareness actions. Aligned with the citizen science approach, these training sessions stimulated a school community awakening to science. Stages were conducted to introduce children to the habits of native stingless bees and the ecosystem services they provide. Initially, a children's film was shown in a school cinema, encouraging the search for information about bee life in general. Subsequently, the focus shifted to a deeper understanding of the selected species. Videos featuring reports from beekeepers and playful activities were used to facilitate understanding of the differences between the native species and Africanized bees, already familiar to the children. Interactions with a Jataí bee nest box installed in the school were established, and routines with these organisms were developed. Aspects of hive organization, the importance of pollinators for nature, and their influence on food security were discussed. Students reflected on the improper use of pesticides and their effects on bee populations, particularly regarding this species conservation. The activities will be registered in a digital interface created by BEESNESS partnerships to show

up the learning on the project. The herein environmental education experiences indicate that direct interactions with nature, including beekeeping activities and a deeper understanding of ecological relationships, may promote a sense of responsibility for biodiversity conservation, for valuing native bee species.

References:

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